

Behavioral Management of Parents and Teachers and the Student's Performance under the new normal

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Abstract: This research assessed the behavior management practices and learners' behavior at home in relation to learners' academic performance in identified schools in the Municipality of Trinidad, Bohol Division during School Year 2020-2021. The data revealed that although there is no significant relationship between behavior management practices of the parents and academic performance findings shows that the academic performance of the learners was above average. However, it can be noted that there is a significant relationship between learners' behavior and students' academic performance. Moreover, time-out was the topmost utilize behavior management of the parents and modeling was the least used. Followed by consequences, reinforcement and modeling. It can also be noted that the most common perceived behavioral problem of the learners argues with their parents. This implies, that there is a need to strengthen the behavior management practices of the parents to promote responsible and respectful learners. The researchers highly recommend that a constant communication with the teacher and parents will be necessary to address learners' behavior. Further, training and workshops must also be employed in the school with parents to be familiar with the new behavior management strategies.

Keywords: Behavior Management, Students' performance, New normal education

1. Introduction

The shutdown of schools, compounded by the associated public health and economic crises, poses major challenges to our students and their teachers. Our public education system was not built, nor prepared, to cope with a situation like this we lack the structures to sustain effective teaching and learning during the shutdown and to provide the safety net supports that many children receive in school. While we do not know the exact impacts, we do know that children's academic performance is deteriorating during the pandemic, along with their progress on other developmental

skills. We also know that, given the various ways in which the crisis has widened existing socioeconomic disparities and how these disparities affect learning and educational outcomes, educational inequities are growing (Garcia & Weiss, 2020).

Moreover, there is a substantial research base about students' ability to learn is as much affected by their inter and intrapersonal behavior as it is by their academic skills. In a classroom environment, teachers can employ practices to manage students' day-to-day behavior. But many parents and caregivers may find behavior management challenging while adjusting to virtual or at-home education. This can be especially difficult as many children deal with emotional challenges like increased anxiety or stress as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic. Parents and caregivers of children with behavioral disorders like ADHD may also face unique challenges during this time (APA, 2020).

Moreover, the current downturn is unique, and in most ways, it is much more severe than any we have experienced in recent history. In the literature, different terms have been used to describe problematic behaviors of students. For instance, student misconduct to disciplinary violations in school, for instance, tardiness, vandalism, fighting, stealing, and drinking on campus. When there are explicit rules and regulations in school and classroom, violation of these is apparently a “misbehavior or misconduct or discipline problem.” Nevertheless, a particular behavior is viewed as problematic may not necessarily be rule breaking, but inappropriate or disturbing in the classroom setting. For instance, daydreaming in class, not completing homework, talking in class, lesson disruption, bullying, and rudeness to the teacher are named as “problem behaviors”, “behavior problems,” or “disruptive behaviors”. (Sun & Shek, 2012).

Moreover, Zakaria, Reupert, & Sharma (2013) stated that, “Classroom management is an essential skill for teachers to acquire, for teachers’ own well-being and for students’ academic progress and wellbeing. Similarly, classroom behavior is one of the critical challenges that educators face today, as schools are far more convoluted than they were in previous years. More learners are coming to class with social problems than ever before and teachers face the test of coping with their actions as key movers (Kuhfeld et al., 2020). Disruptive actions are without a doubt one of the key difficulties for teachers and parents. Research consistently demonstrates that misbehavior among students disrupts classroom order and learning, adversely affecting academic achievement (Wang, 2015). In addition, a student survey conducted in Norway, it is evident that much time is used on other activities than learning. 30 percent of the student that answered this survey report that other students often or always disturb them in class.

Moreover, classroom discipline encompasses complex interactions among teacher variables, student variables, school variables, because classroom discipline is structured around the parceling of power in a specific public space, the issues become important politically and educationally (Pane et. al (2014). Today’s learning environment are much more complicated than in years past because some learners do not respect teachers, more learners come to school with behavioral problem than ever before (Lumanug, 2015). Disrespect for rules and procedures, wandering around the room, talking out of turn, passive engagement in the classroom, disruption of classmates’ work and moving the furniture in the classroom, are just some of a wide

range of behaviors referred by teachers as classroom misbehavior (Briesch, Briesch, & Chafouleas, 2015).

According to Imad (2020) there are growing numbers of colleges and universities all across the country including Dartmouth College, Rice University and Stanford University, among many others are temporarily canceling their face-to-face classes to deal with the impact of the COVID-19 situation. The conversations on our campuses, as well as on professional Listservs, have turned to the topic of academic continuity plans as the nation continues to deal with the impact of COVID-19. As I look through the materials put together by various teaching and learning centers and instructional technology groups, I have noticed that the resources have focused almost exclusively on the how of technology: tools to record lectures, create discussions and proctor exams. Yet while the technological know-how to virtually connect with our students is necessary, it is not sufficient to continue the teaching and learning endeavor.

In the Philippines, few would argue that the state of our education system has plenty of room for improvement. However, developing a plan to take schools in the right direction is easier said than done. The first challenge lies in identifying underlying problems keeping students from learning today especially our education is beyond classroom (Distance Education /home education). Observations and actual experiences have shown that common problems met within the school environment pertain to behavior and thus, also affects the facilitation of the learning process of the students. Hence, developing intervention sooner will help to mitigate unwanted activity and teach learners the proper ways to communicate with other learners. The researcher assumes that prevention is better than cure, and thus it is on this basis that prevention will be pursued in order to recognize and provide intervention to any student behavior, invoking assistance from parents and teachers.

2. Purpose of the Study

This research assessed the learner's behavior management practices of teachers and parents' and learners' performance under the new normal in the identified schools in Bohol Division. It sought to answer the following questions; The level of the teacher's behavior council practices as perceived by the teacher's intervention and learners in terms of reinforcements, time-outs, modeling and consequence and the relationship between the behavior council practices and learners' academic performance.

3. Research Methodology

3.1 Design

This research used descriptive research method to gather the information about the level of behavior counsel practices of Elementary learners as perceived by the respondent's group in the identified Schools in Bohol Division together with sets of questionnaires as data gathering instruments. The data gathered used processed and analyzed utilizing the appropriate statistical software with 0.05 level of significance. The results of the study served as basis for an action plan. The research started on the Orientation Of The Respondents On Current Study. The Researcher Used The Input-Process-Output Approach

3.2 Research Respondents

The research environment was the Hinlayagan Ilaya Elementary School, Guinobatan Elementary School, Soom Integrated School- Elementary Department and Tagum Sur Elementary School. The school is government owned, located in the Municipality of Trinidad, Bohol Division. The respondents of the study were the grade 5 and 6 learners and their parents. They were taken through the use of purposive sampling, those learners and parents who are free and accessible were the one who participated in the study.

3.3 Instruments

The main instrument in this study was adopted from the website a researcher made questionnaire. Based on the computation, with the Cronbach's Alpha is 0.772, this indicates a high level of consistency for our scale. Hence, the questionnaire is therefore reliable.

4. Results and Discussion

Table 1. Academic Performance of the Learners

Learners Performance	Frequency	Percentage
Superior (90-95)	271	39
Very Good (85-89)	321	45
Good (80-84)	65	9
Fair (75-79)	39	7
Failure (Below 74)	0	0
Total	696	100

Table 1 shows the learners academic performance. Based on the data gathered, it was reflected that most of the learners 321 or 45% obtained a rating of very good, this implies that learners were striving hard to have a higher grade. However, out of 39 or 7% obtained a rating of fair. The researchers believe that these results were affected by different factors that hinders them to achieve a higher grade, this includes from personal to environment. According to Mazana et al. (2019), Suson & Ermac (2020), they believed that the attitudes of the learners indicated their perceptions and feelings about a particular subject. Consequently, a learner who has a positive attitude towards his subject, teacher or schooling as a whole seeks to study more than a learner with a negative attitude.

Table 2. Reinforcement

Reinforcements	WM
Compliment the learner on good behavior or performance.	3.12
Awarding token for appropriate behavior	3.07
Give positive comments written on pupil's work.	3.05
Grand Mean	3.08

The finding of the study as presented in table 9 shows that reinforcement got an overall weighted mean of 3.08 which verbally described as often. Compliment the learner on good behavior or performance got the highest mean of 3.12 which verbally described as often, while the statement gives positive comments written on pupil's work was rated lowest which also verbally described as often. This implies that

parents were able to apply reinforcement strategy to the learners when they encountered behavioral problem during studying sessions.

According to Scott (2018), the behavior therapy is often used to suppress or minimize the capacity of adults or children to act as psycho therapeutic intervention. While some therapies concentrate on modifying cognitive patterns that can influence behavior. In addition, Cherry (2018) pointed out that strengthening would increase the probability of a reaction. Note that strengthening is characterized by its impact on behavior, improves or strengthens the response. Strengtheners as one of conduct regulation were also very useful in resolving the unwanted actions of learners.

Table 3. Time-outs

Time-outs	WM
Having private conversation with the learner and address the disruptive behavior immediately.	3.12
Do not allow the child/pupil to access the TV duding study hours.	3.10
Do not allow the child/pupil to access YouTube during study hours.	3.11
Weighted Mean	3.11

In terms of time-outs, the results achieve an overall weighted mean of 3.11 which verbally described as often. Based on the data, all practices were rated often. The statement refers to having private conversation with the learner and address the disruptive behavior immediately got the highest mean of 3.12 which verbally described as often, while the statement refers to do not allow the child/pupil to access the TV duding study hours got the lowest mean of 3.10 which also verbally described as often. This indicates that parents were able to provide appropriate responded on learners' behavior. Markham (2019) concluded that timeouts are successful, but only temporary, in getting people to cooperate. The children who were disciplined were more likely to misbehave after being recorded being out-of-seat, than those who were not. One must be realistic about discipline-related interactions between children and parents and teachers. There should be no harm or injury that each other. Discipline is about teaching. It's not about physical punishment. Moreover, children are positively isolated by time-out. Even when presented in a loving manner, time outs teach a child that when he makes a mistake or has a hard time, he will be forced to be by himself. This implies that timeouts as one of behavior management is not ideal in handling learners' undesirable behavior.

Table 4. Modeling

Modeling	WM
Use polite language when talking to the learner and to the people around you.	3.06
Do not shout when the learners did something wrong instead give comfort.	2.99
Sleep early and avoid too much use of gadgets.	3.10
Grand Mean	3.05

The third practices that parents applied if they encountered learners' behavioral problem was modeling. Table 4 shows that modeling appropriate behavior got an

overall weighted mean of 3.05 which verbally described as often. The statement refers to sleep early and avoid too much use of gadgets got the highest mean of 3.10 which verbally described as often, while the statement do not shout when the learners did something wrong instead give comfort got the lowest weighted mean of 2.99 which verbally also verbally described as often. This implied that parents were able to model appropriate behavior moreover, being a role model might daunt our students, but it's a great opportunity to teach students how to see themselves positively. Modeling is thus important for learners to interact.

Table 5. Consequences

Reinforcements	WM
Giving verbal warning to loss of rewards	3.07
Reprimand the learners on disruptive behavior.	3.11
Removing privileges (e.g., miss out on free time, watching movies, play with friends, etc.).	3.06
Grand Mean	3.09

Table 5 shows the behavioral management practices in terms of consequences. Based on the data, consequences got a final weighted mean of 3.09 which verbally described as often. The statement refers to reprimand the learners on disruptive behavior got the highest mean of 3.11 while the statement refers to Removing privileges (e.g., miss out on free time, watching movies, play with friends, etc.) got the lowest weighted mean of 3.06. Ramaswamy and Bergin (2009) says that it is important and must be part of our classroom. We do a lot to help them protect their life if one of our primary educational aims is to prepare students for life. However, many students lack innate motivation and are not strong enough to overcome their lack of interest in winning a prize. These students also have implications for their success. Don't misinterpret again, please. They need a lot more interesting education, passion, inspiration and so on. But sometimes children only need to know that if they do not do as they should, there are consequences. It is also advised, therefore, that teachers in the classroom must also use the consequences to train students that any undesirable activity has consequences.

The Relationship Between Academic Performance and Parent's Management Behavior

Table 6. Chi-square tests to test the null hypothesis of independence

I) Reinforcement

Variables	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
English * Compliments	2.238 ^a	2	.327
English * Awarding_Tokens	.840 ^a	2	.657
English * Positive_Comments	.043 ^a	2	.978
Math * Compliments	3.788 ^a	4	.435
Math * Awarding_Tokens	2.257 ^a	4	.689
Math * Positive_Comments	3.295 ^a	4	.510
Science * Compliments	1.208 ^a	2	.547
Science * Awarding_Tokens	1.547 ^a	2	.461

Science * Positive_Comments	.349 ^a	2	.840
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a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 17.00.

The Pearson Chi-square P-values are all above the significance level hence we accept the null hypotheses in all the pairwise chi-square tests. There is therefore no significant relationship between Academic Performance and Reinforcement practices.

Table 7. Time-outs

Variables	Value	df	Asymp. Sig.
English * Private Conversation	1.757 ^a	2	.415
English * Disallowed Access to TV	3.824 ^a	2	.148
English * Disallowed Youtube	.185 ^a	2	.912
Math * Private Conversation	3.181 ^a	4	.528
Math * Disallowed Access to TV	6.237 ^a	4	.182
Math * Disallowed YouTube	2.544 ^a	4	.637
Science * Private Conversation	.827 ^a	2	.661
Science * Disallowed Access to TV	.114 ^a	2	.945
Science * Disallowed YouTube	1.046 ^a	2	.593

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 17.00.

The two-sided P-values are all above 0.05. We therefore retain the null hypotheses. This implies that there is no significant relationship between time-out activities and academic performance.

Table 8. Modelling

Variables	Value	df	Asymp. Sig.
English * Polite_Language	1.880 ^a	2	.391
English * Not shouting to learner	3.384 ^a	2	.184
English * Early Sleeping	1.674 ^a	2	.433
Math * Polite_Language	8.716 ^a	4	.069
Math * Not shouting to learner	5.043 ^a	4	.283
Math * Early Sleeping	6.118 ^a	4	.190
Science * Polite_Language	.286 ^a	2	.867
Science * Not shouting to learner	.355 ^a	2	.838
Science * Early Sleeping	.303 ^a	2	.859

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 17.00.

The P-values are all above the significant level. We therefore retain the null hypotheses. This implies that there is no significant relationship between modelling activities and academic performance.

Table 9. Consequences

Variables	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
English * Verbal Warning	4.829 ^a	2	.089

English * Reprimanding	.450 ^a	2	.798
English * Removing Privileges	2.537 ^a	2	.281
Math * Verbal Warning	2.280 ^a	4	.684
Math * Reprimanding	.517 ^a	4	.972
Math * Removing Privileges	9.205 ^a	4	.056
Science * Verbal Warning	.478 ^a	2	.787
Science * Reprimanding	1.724 ^a	2	.422
Science * Removing Privileges	.609 ^a	2	.737

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 17.00.

The P-values are all above the significant level (0.05). We therefore accept the null hypotheses. This implies that there is no significant relationship between the consequences and academic performance.

The Relationship Between Learner's Behavior at Home and Academic Performance

Table 10. Learners Behavior and Academic Performance

Variables	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
English * Argue with Parents	6.061 ^a	1	.014
English * Argue with Siblings	2.205 ^a	1	.138
English * Use mobiles	2.935 ^a	1	.087
English * Noisy environment	1.185 ^a	1	.276
English * Procrastination	7.533 ^a	1	.006
English * Unable to complete module	2.734 ^a	1	.098
English * Untimely answering of tasks	1.466 ^a	1	.226
English * Not understanding module instructions	9.227 ^a	1	.002
English * Short retention span	5.785 ^a	1	.016
English * Short attention in focussing on task	4.003 ^a	1	.045
English * Playing online games	.081 ^a	1	.776
English * Staying up and waking up late	.386 ^a	1	.534
English * Fighting with siblings	1.097 ^a	1	.295
English * Not listening to parents	.337 ^a	1	.562
English * Disrespectful behaviour	1.097 ^a	1	.295
English * Food related problems	.577 ^a	1	.448
English * Inappropriate usage of electronic gadgets	4.965 ^a	1	.026
English * Copying answer key without reading mdl	.854 ^a	1	.355
English * Temper tantrums	1.531 ^a	1	.216
English * Fan of watching TV without doing module	.486 ^a	1	.486

English * Use of inappropriate language	.205 ^a	1	.651
Math * Argue with parents	.798 ^a	1	.671
Math * Argue with Siblings	.242 ^a	2	.866
Math * Use mobiles	.998 ^a	2	.607
Math * Noisy environment	9.384 ^a	2	.009
Math * Procrastination	2.105 ^a	2	.349
Math * Unable to complete modules	2.797 ^a	2	.247
Math * Untimely answering of tasks	.908 ^a	2	.635
Math * Not understanding module instructions	.938 ^a	2	.626
Math * Short retention span	.034 ^a	2	.983
Math * Short attention in focussing on task	1.034 ^a	2	.596
Math * Playing online games	1.742 ^a	2	.418
Math * Staying up and waking up late	.482 ^a	2	.786
Math * Fighting with siblings	2.714 ^a	2	.257
Math * Not listening to parents	5.939 ^a	2	.051
Math * Disrespectful behaviour	.979 ^a	2	.613
Math * Food related problems	1.408 ^a	2	.495
Math * Inappropriate usage of electronic gadgets	.853 ^a	2	.653
Math * Copying answer key without reading mdl	1.098 ^a	2	.577
Math * Temper tantrums	.443 ^a	2	.801
Math * Fan of watching TV without doing module	.998 ^a	2	.607
Math * Use of inappropriate language	2.048 ^a	2	.359
Science * Argue with parents	1.412 ^a	1	.235
Science * Argue with Siblings	.507 ^a	1	.477
Science * Use mobiles	2.403 ^a	1	.121
Science * Noisy environment	3.936 ^a	1	.047
Science * Procrastination	1.650 ^a	1	.199
Science * Unable to complete modules	.040 ^a	1	.842
Science * Untimely answering of tasks	3.117 ^a	1	.077
Science * Not understanding module instructions	.246 ^a	1	.620
Science * Short retention span	.012 ^a	1	.913
Science * Short attention in focussing on task	.234 ^a	1	.629
Science * Playing online games	2.374	1	.123
Science * Staying up and waking up late	.724 ^a	1	.395
Science * Fighting with siblings	.876 ^a	1	.349
Science * Not listening to parents	1.135 ^a	1	.287
Science * Disrespectful behaviour	.345 ^a	1	.557
Science * Food related problems	.045 ^a	1	.832
Science * Inappropriate usage of electronic gadgets	.139 ^a	1	.709
Science * Copying answer key without reading mdl	.492 ^a	1	.483

Science * Temper tantrums	.286 ^a	1	.592
Science * Fan of watching TV without doing module	.257 ^a	1	.612
Science * Use of inappropriate language	.000 ^a	1	.996

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 17.00.

The highlighted rows show the pairwise variables whose chi-square values are significant at 0.05 level. This implies therefore that there is a significant relationship between performance in English and Arguing with Parents, Procrastination, Not understanding module instructions, short retention span, short attention in focusing on task, and Inappropriate usage of electronic gadgets have a significant relationship. These variables therefore have an effect on the performance of English. There is also a significant relationship between Math and Noisy environment, Science and Noisy environment. This implies that noisy environment has a significant effect on performance of Math and Science.

5. Discussions

Findings have shown that learners grade level has shown more than half of or 423 or 61% of the learners were grade 6 and the remaining 273 or 39% were in grade 5 and in terms of learner's performance findings show that most of the learners 321 or 45% obtained a rating of very good and 39 or 7% got the lowest rating of fair. Meanwhile, in terms of transferred management practices from teachers to parents, findings show that reinforcement, timeouts, modeling, and consequences were perceived effective management practices applied by parents in the new normal of education. In terms of learner behavior at home the statement learner argues with their parents garnered the highest mean, while not able to complete their module at the given time were perceived as the least behavior problem.

For the significant relationship, findings show there was no significant relationship on behavioral practices and academic performance. However, in terms of learner's behavior at home, finding shows that there is a significant relationship between performance in English and Arguing with Parents, Procrastination, Not understanding module instructions, short retention span, short attention in focusing on task, and Inappropriate usage of electronic gadgets have a significant relationship. These variables therefore have an effect on the performance of English. There is also a significant relationship between Math and Noisy environment, Science and Noisy environment. This implies that noisy environment has a significant effect on performance of Math and Science.

6. Conclusion

This research assessed the behavior management practices and learners' behavior in relation to learner academic performance. Based on the data analysis, it was indicated that the behavior management practices have moderate influence on learners' performance, however, learners' behavior at home does contribute to the overall learner's performance. By recognizing the impact of this results, it is very important to provide appropriate support to the learners. Moreover, the results implied that despite covid-19 pandemic and new set-up of education, learners were still motivated to learn.

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